

The Impact of Implementing a Wound Care Protocol In the Jail Setting

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Background

- Nearly 870 of every 100,000 U.S. adult citizens are currently incarcerated
- Skin infections are an identified health burden across healthcare systems and similarly common finding among inmates
- Though international guidelines exist for management of chronic and acute wounds, fewer are available for those that are acute in nature and are outdated and not well supported by more recent literature

Purpose

To develop a tailored, evidence-based wound protocol in a Los Angeles County Jail urgent care clinic for incarcerated patients

Setting

- Urgent care in the Los Angeles County Jail in Downtown LA
- This jail is the world's largest jail system, with about 16,500 inmates on any given day

Methodology

- Plan-Do-Study-Act framework
- Exhaustive literature search across databases, including search of current wound clinical practice guidelines from the CDC and a professional organization specific to wounds and correctional health
- A site-specific tailored approach was conducted, including gathering team input from advanced practice providers and chief physician of the correctional health site

Plan-Do-Study-Act Framework

Wound Detection/Treatment Algorithm

Results

- The plan phase of PDSA was executed with a robust plan for future implementation and evaluation for stages do, study, and act
- An evidence-based wound detection and treatment algorithm was developed from literature, professional practice recommendations, and team input from the site
- Urgent care providers gave input allowing for tailoring of the final tool to the LA County Jail setting to increase the prompt detection of complex wounds and referrals to a higher level of care when indicated

Recommendations

- Use of PDSA framework to implement and evaluate the developed screening and treatment tool tailored to the Los Angeles County Jail urgent care setting
- Findings of the ongoing QI work in this setting will contribute to mitigation efforts to reduce risk and improve health of this highly vulnerable population

Limitations

- The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic led to staffing changes at the clinic site
- Due to the pandemic, although a robust plan was developed, the new protocol could not be implemented and evaluated
- Many employees contracted COVID-19 impacting the number of staff available to give input on the developed tool

Conclusions

- Utilization of an acute wound care protocol aimed at screening wounds may help improve the detection of infected wounds in inmates
- Inmates with high-risk behaviors such as those who inject drugs and self drain infected wounds are the groups most at risk for adverse outcomes in jails
- Reducing the number of undetected wounds in the jail setting through evidence-based practice is vital to improve the quality of life for this vulnerable population

References

